

PARENTAL MOTIVATIONS AND INVOLVEMENT: A DEVELOPING COUNTRY PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract:

The paper reports qualitative results of a mixed design investigation. Qualitative data is collated by means of semi-structured interviews from 33 parents of children from four schools in Northern region of Ghana. The sample included from 16 parents from deprived districts and 17 parents from non-deprived districts whose children attended both public and private basic schools within these districts. The key objective of the study was to explore Motivations for involvement in deprived and non-deprived districts in a developing country context and also to identify some barriers to both school based and home based involvement. The findings suggest that parent's Attitude were the foremost motivation factor that influences their involvement in their child's education. This was followed by Social norm (SN) and Perceived behavioural control (PBC). It was found that some difference did exist for influence PBC and SN on parents across deprived and non-deprived districts. It was also found that parent home involvement activities varied with the most dominant activities setting time to study, as assisting with homework, and selecting television programmes for children, though marginal differences were observed across district type. With regards to school activities most parents largely limited themselves to PTA meetings and communications with school teachers. It was also found barriers to PI included the lack of time due to work schedules, the lack knowledge on homework, and financial constraints, based on these findings some recommendations to help improve parental involvement are presented.

Keywords: subjective norms, deprived districts, non-deprived districts, basic schools, school involvement

1. Introduction

Parental Involvement is defined in the current research as parent behaviours related to the child's schooling that can be observed as manifestations of their commitment to their child's educational affairs. Extant literature relating to educational outcomes has shown

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that outcomes of education especially at the basic level approximately (at par) hinges on the parents' involvement just it does for factors like school tuition, school climate. This is largely because confidence and motivations of children toward education at the basic level of education is heavily linked with the level of the parental involvement in the child education. For example, Eisenberg and Wolchik (1992) have shown that the competences and performance of children below 11 years are known to be heavily associated with the parents Involvement. The rationale of getting parents involved at the basic level of education is, therefore, to bring on board the additional impact which parents would bring in order to improve on school quality.

In response to numerous studies in several developed countries including North America, United Kingdom, and Europe that have demonstrated the positive connection of performance and Parental Involvement, policies have been put in place to increase Parental Involvement as part of an overall strategy to improve academic performance and to close the achievement gap (e.g., "No Child Left Behind Act," 2002; Miksic, 2015; Malkawi & Smadi, 2016).

The situation appears somewhat different in less developed nations, particularly in Africa, where this "advertised" parameter of educational quality happens to be amongst the least understood (Mungai, 2015). In Ghana, like in other less developed nations in Africa, educational initiatives and policies undertaken have not given much attention to the role of Parental Involvement can play in achieving quality education (Mungai, 2015, Gyamfi & Pobbi 2016). The Ghana Education Service Act, 1995 (Act 506) as part of Ghana's decentralisation policy emphasizes a collaborative approach in which all stakeholders including parents and Teachers Association have spell-out roles and responsibilities in the planning process. Although the Act (Act 506) is meant to encourage active community participation and for that matter active participation of parents in their children's education there is no clear policy document on PI nationally, or at the school level (Vanderpuyue, 2013). Symbiotic of the lack of strategic direction is the fact that there is a lack of interest by most Ghanaian parents in the education of their children (Pryor & Ampah, 2003; Nyarko, 2007; Chowa, Ansong, & Osei-Akoto, 2012; Gyamfi, 2016; 2018).

Aside the lack of direction an important issue which is peculiar in such regions is the disparities that exist in the socio-economic status of parents in deprived districts as compared to those in non-deprived districts which according to Boateng and Ansah (2014) threaten the achievement of overall educational objectives. Literature including Eccle and Harold (1996), Griffith (1998) have also shown a strong link between SES and parents' involvement in schools. A valid question which emanate in such a background/situation is what then could effectively motivate these parents to actively engage in the education of their children?

Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1997) have investigated some motivations for involvement in American homes. Literature has, however, shown that parental behaviours or largely hinges on their perceptions of their roles toward their child education, but this is also related to the culture, perceptions, habits and social influence (Grolnick & Slowiaczek, 1997; Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 1997; Cid, Wilcox, Lippman,

& Whitney, 2010; Avvisati, Besbas & Guyon, 2010), hence, these factors may substantially differ especially in less developed country context due to cultural differences.

1.1 Objectives of the study

- Compare the motivations for parental involvement at school across non-deprived and deprived districts
- To determine home and School based activities parents get involved to support their children education.
- To identify barriers that affect parental involvement among deprived and non-deprived districts

2. Literature Review

Key factors highlighted as influencing parental involvement include parent Perceived behavioural control, Parents attitudes and beliefs, and Subjective Norms. Ajzen (1991) defined perceived control as one's own perception of his/her ability to perform a certain behaviour thereby producing desired outcomes. For parents to involve themselves in the education of their children both at school and at home Bandura (1997) posit that they must possess expertise or experience needful to perform a task in some educational activities. Studies including Pena (2000), Lee and Brown (2006), Smith, Stern, and Shatrova (2008), Jafarov (2015) have in similar vein linked parental involvement with parental level of education. Lee and Brown (2006), Smith, Stern, and Shatrova (2008) posit that parents with higher college degrees showed more enthusiasm in getting involved with issues pertaining to the development of their children as compared to their colleagues with low or no formal education. Pena (2000) finding, on the other hand, reveals that parents with a low level of education were more willing to volunteer to participate in school activities as compared to their educated counterparts. According to Pena (2000), educated and less educated parents ascribed positively to the importance of parental involvement in the children's education.

Attitude and beliefs about child education include beliefs and feeling that a certain action like home involvement activities when engaged in will lead to positive outcomes for their children (Ajzen 1991). In a study by Bruning, Schraw, Norby, and Ronning (2004) the authors posit that engagement is contingent upon the belief that goals are attainable and a belief that participation in an activity increases the probability that a goal will be met. Applying Bandura's (1997) definition of Self-efficacy to Parental Involvement, Walker, Wilkins, Dallaire, Sandler, & Hoover-Dempsey (2005) suggested that parents make involvement decisions based on their thinking about the outcomes which are likely to follow their involvement activities. Alghazo (2016) hence mentions that attitude and beliefs of parent could be a key factor in explaining the motivations of Parental Involvement.

Subjective norms were defined as the opinions and accepted behaviours of the people surrounding an individual who is to engage in a certain behaviour. These opinions and behaviours can lead to social pressure on the parent thus influence a parent

toward a certain behaviour. Parent standards with regards to their roles in education is contingent on cultures and societal influence (Avvisati, Besbas, & Guyon, 2010). Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (1997), and Bracke and Corts (2012) posit that parents' beliefs about raising their child's development stems from parents' societal experiences or better acceptable behaviours of relatives and community. Donkor, Issaka, and Asante (2013) also highlight the role of culture in inhibiting the parent support for child education. Evidence in less developed countries have revealed that due to societal perception and norms some parents were hesitant in sending their children, especially the girl child, to school since other did not see it as necessary (Adu, 1999). For example, a farmer in a deprived community would prefer to have the child join them on their farms of fishing trip or even to the market since other farmers, fishermen and market women do so. However, if everyone related to these parents send their children to school then they will be compelled to send their children to school. Specific invitations from the child school and from the child also serve as social influence on parents to get involved in the child's education (Kohl, Lengua, & McMahon, 2002).

Nyarko's (2011) study on low-income household, selected Ghanaian youth from ages twelve to eighteen. The research found that Ghanaian parents do often engage in their children's schooling in various forms although their involvement are mostly dominantly home. Pryor and Ampiah's (2003) also found that more Ghanaian parents are some extent involved in ensuring their children complete their homework. Similarly, Gyamfi and Pobbi (2016) found that parent seem to pay more attention to Select TV programme for child, set time for children to come back from school and Monitors homework. The researchers, however, noted that parental involvement especially in monitoring activities generally remain low among parents as some are still at work by the time their children get home from school (Gyamfi & Pobbi, 2016; 2018). Notwithstanding, Brooke (2009) and (Donkor, 2010) posits that parents acknowledge the relevance of education for their children in the modern society. For example Brooke (2009, p.43) reported that about four out of ten Ghanaian parents who participated in his study saw primary education "*as the starting point for a protracted educational career or for 'progress', or as a means to securing employment*".

Although many studies exist on PI and child performance only few explain how parents are motivated to get involved. Again, these few studies have failed to examine how the differences in district types in developing countries can influence parent motivation toward child education. This is particular of interest in a context where the disparities in the socio-economic status parent due on their district location do have the potential to influence their attitudes, PBC and SN.

3. Material and Methods

The researcher developed a semi-structured interview guide in relation to the set objectives of the current parent involvement study. A pilot study was conducted to test reliability the instruments. Collection of data for the study started in June, 2019. Prior to that a letter of introduction from my school (AIT) was sent to all the District Educational

offices which had oversight responsibility for the participating schools and to the Headteachers of the participating schools in each region in May–June 2019 for their consent. Upon approval the cover letters from the district Education Directors and that of AIT were sent to the selected schools and given to Head masters to seek approval and date when the survey can be conducted in their schools. Based on the schedules from various districts and headteachers, and with the help of trained data collection personnel questionnaires were administered and interviews were conducted from June to July 2019. Selected parents were invited to the school with the help of class teachers for the interviews and also to fill the questionnaires. Only parents who were willing to partake in interviews were selected. Parents were asked a number of questions relating to their level of involvement in their child's education, on factors which motivate their involvement, and on factors which serve as barriers to their involvement).

4. Results and Discussion

Three main themes were investigated in the study. The first theme was with regards to motivations for PI. The next theme relates Parental involvement activities in both deprived and non-deprived districts. The final theme relates barriers to parents' involvement to child education. Results are presented in coherence with the objectives of the study.

OB1: To Compare the Motivations for Parental Involvement at School across Deprived and Deprived Districts.

To address the research objective the researcher first sought to explore first from parents' issues that motivated their involvement (both home and school based). Next the research proceeds to investigate specifically how these three motivational factors attitude and beliefs, Perceived Behavioural control and Subjective norms do influence their involvement in their child's education

4.1 Motivations to parental involvement

To explore the general factors that motivate parent's involvements in their children's education, parents were asked: What are some reasons why you get involved in your child's education? In response to the question five main issues or factors were mentioned by parents.

These were: for the improvement of the child's performances in school, to help the child to secure a better future, assist and encourage child's learning, to help improve the child behaviour, to help child understand the importance of education, and finally, it was their responsibility to do so.

The most influential factor extracting from parents' views was to help the child to improve their performance in school. This accounted for an estimated 36.4% of all responses provided by parents. However, responses of some parent suggest that they are quite relaxed with their involvement until they saw that child are not performing as expected.

Some responses of parent as follows:

"[I get involved] to help her to perform better in school, especially when her teacher complains to me about her performance." [Parent 20, deprived]

"Getting involved is valuable to my child's performance." [Parent 9, non-deprived]

The second most motivational factors outlined by parents was the need to assist and encourage child's learning, and to help the child to secure a better future for the child. This account for an estimated percentage of 28.2% of all responses provided by parents respectively.

Some responses of parents as follows:

"...to encourage them to learn to let the child know the importance of education to help the child in difficult assignments." [Parent 3, non-deprived]

"...to make him achieve his educational goals, and also to make him financially fit for the Future." [Parent 5, deprived]

"...to ensure she attains a higher standard in her education" [Parent 6 deprived]

"...to ensure my child excels in her academic career" [Parent 30, deprived]

The remaining factors mentioned by parents as reasons why they get involved in the child education was it was their responsibility to do so (7.6 %, of all responses provided by parents), and for the child to understand the importance of education.

Some responses of parents as follows:

"...its my duty to get involved in my child's education because of the fees I pay" [Parent 21, deprived]

"She is my responsibility and must ensure she is getting the right education. I also want her to build her self-confidence." [Parent 33, deprived]

A critical examination of responses across district type (ie for deprived and no deprived districts) shows that there was not so much differences in the views of parents in deprived districts from those in non-deprived district. This is represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Multiple Bar chart of Parents Views on Reasons they Get Involved in Child Education

These factors outlined by parents suggest that parents were mostly motivated by two broad motivational issues toward child education. These were the perception on outcomes (attitude and belief) of education, and their duties as parents toward the child. The most relevant factor which underlines parent involvement among deprived and non-deprived parents was the attitude and belief of their parents.

In relation to these results, researchers including Brooke (2009) and Donkor (2010) have mentioned that Ghanaian Parents still know the relevance of education for their children although, Nyarko (2011) and Pryor and Ampiah's (2003), Gyamfi and Pobbi (2016) have shown that there is low involvement of parents in child education. Brooke (2009) specifically noted that about four out of ten Ghanaian parents saw primary education as the foundation of a success academic carrier and also means for securing a good job in future.

Next, the study specifically sought to investigate the attitudes, perceived behavioural control and Subjective norms do influence parent's behaviours.

4.2 Attitudes and Beliefs

With regards to the attitudes and beliefs of parents towards child education, parents were asked: How useful do you think getting involved in a child education is?

The result generally reveal that parents believed that their involvement was mostly useful for the improvement their child attitude toward learning both at home and in school. This represented 37.2% (of the entire views provided by parents interviewed). The next most occurring view of parents was to improve the child's Performances in school. This accounted for 32.6% of all responses provided by parents.

Some responses from some participants were as follows:

"it has helped them to perform well in school" [Parent 2, non-deprived]

"It is useful. It helps to identify the problems the child faces and to know their performances." [Parent 3, non-deprived]

"...it help the child to improve their behaviour and performance." [Parent 4, deprived]

"Well it more useful for my child's education, it helps my child to be more serious about her education." [Parent 8, deprived]

The third most occurring view of parents was to improve the child's self confidence in school. This accounted for 18.6% of all responses provided by parents.

A response given by a parent:

"It makes my child look confident and perform well." [Parent 28, deprived]

Remaining issues outlined by parents with regard to the usefulness of their involvement were to get informed on the progress of child and to improve their behaviour at school. The views accounted for 9.3% and 2.3% (of all responses) respectively.

A critical examination of responses to how useful getting involved is across district type is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Multiple Bar Chart of Attitude and Belief of Parents across District type

The chart in figure 2 shows the most useful reasons across district type were improving child attitude to learning, and improving child performance. There were however some differences with regard to the remaining items outlined by parents across district type, for example, more parents in deprived district (26.1%) than those in non-deprived districts (10%) claimed that their involvement help to build up their children's.

Self confidence in school and also that they were informed on the progress of their child when they get involved in their child's education

The result generally suggest that parents were aware of some relevance of getting involved in school which is support by Brooke (2009) and Donkor (2010). The results are also in line with Bruning, Schraw, Norby, and Ronning (2004) who posit that parental behaviours to child education is associated with the belief that participation will increases the chance of meeting the learning goals, key of which is performances of their children.

4.3 Subjective Norms

The researcher further sought to investigate if and how parents' involvement was influenced by Subjective norm. Parents were asked: Is your involvement influenced by expectations of people including family, neighbours, child's school etc.? Please explain how.

Analysis of the distribution of responses provided on if parents were influenced by expectations of people around you (social influence) show that most were influence by their society. The view accounted for 50.0 % of responses provided by parents. Explaining how societal norms and belief influenced parents who responded to "yes", parent noted that the most Subjective norm issue that influenced their involvement was the expectations of close relatives to enroll and ensure their children attend school (40% of all responses). The next influence was from influence from child's school (33.3%, of all responses). With regard to influences form child school a parent noted how teachers expressed their pleasure with their involvement.

Some responses from some participants were as follows:

"yes, they expect me to take my child to school" [Parent 9, non-deprived]

"yes I am praised [by teachers] when my child reports to school early" [Parent 3, non-deprived]

"yes, the teachers sometimes invite me to discuss child performance in homework" [Parent 25, deprived]

The final issue was influence due to involvement of from neighbours and community (26.7% of all responses). Most of these parents believed the involvement of their neighbours contributed to their child's success.

Some responses from some participants were as follows:

"yes, most of my neighbours always do as I do, they participate in most of their child's school activities and it improves their child's performance." [Parent 8, non-deprived]

"yes, my relatives take their children to school. The school teachers also expect that I come over especially during PTA so we can discuss the child's performances." [Parent 17, non-deprived]

An examination of responses provided per the district type, however, reveal that most parent who responded yes in deprived districts were more influenced by their neighbours and community influence (42.9%) this was the least influential factor for parents in non-deprived districts (12.5%). Some parents also noted how teachers expressed their pleasure with their involvement. A response which suggest that their involvement was welcomed in schools.

Among parents who responded “no” to the question felt it was their duty to be involved in the child education. For example, a parent commented:

“No. I do what is right for my child.” [Parent 4, non-deprived]

The results generally suggest that although some parents did understand the fact that involvement is their responsibility a number of parents were influence by social influence include those from their neighbours, family and teachers from the child school.

These results are in line with Avvisati, Besbas, and Guyon (2010). Bracke and Corts (2012) who explained that subjective norms relating to parental role in child education, include having role models and neighbours that do or do not get involved in their children’s which through experience form better or acceptable behaviours for these parent (Hoover-Dempsey & Sandler, 1997). In other words, if everyone related to these parents send their children to school eventually, these parents will be compelled to send their children to school. Kohl, Lengua, and McMahan (2002) also comment on the need for parent invitations from the child school in influencing parents to get involved in the child’s education

4.4 Perceived Behavioural Control

Do you think that your abilities and Skills influences the way you get involved in your child education? Please explain briefly.

Analysis of the distribution of responses provided on if parents were influenced by their abilities (behavioural control) show that most parents were in support of the fact that their abilities did either positively or negatively influence their involvement in child’s education. The view accounted for 67.7% of all responses provided by parents. A critical examination of responses across district type reveal similar trend in response for parents from deprived (67%) and non-deprived (64.7%) districts.

A follow up question was posed to explain further how parent’s abilities influence their involvement in child education. An analysis of their responses reveals that responses to parent abilities was more limited to home involvement activities relating to their studies and child homework from school.

Some comments are outlined:

“...yes, with my knowledge as a teacher I am able to explain things to my child” [Parent 30, deprived]

"Yes, so much, I am able to help him do his homework, and also make relevant input and contributions during PTA". [Parent 5, non-deprived]

While most parents from non-deprived districts noted that they had some formal education and that they were able to assist the child with their homework (of all "yes" responses), Parents who did not have much formal education noted that they sometimes had difficulties assisting the child with the homework when they did not have an idea of what child's homework was about.

Some comments are outlined:

"...yes, Sometimes I am not able to help much with the homework since I did not have much formal education" [Parent 22, deprived]

"Yes, I am not able to help when I don't have idea about his homework he brings home" [Parent 24, deprived]

Some researchers including Jafarov (2015), Lee and Brown (2006), Smith, Stern, and Shatrova (2008) also report that parents' level of education and school experiences is one factor which can influence the involvement of parents in child education to know how their children are doing and what kind of support they require.

Again, a careful look at responses provided by parent reveal that parents who did not have much education did frequently visit the teachers than educated parents. For example, one parent commented

"Yes, Sometimes I am not able to help much with the homework since I did not have much formal education"[parent 23, deprived] also noted when asked of school involvement activities that "I pay the teacher a visit to discuss child performance...." [Parent 23, deprived district]

The observation is supported by Pena (2000) who noted that parents with a low level of education were more willing to volunteer to participate in school activities as compared to their educated counterparts.

OB2: To Investigate How Parents Involve Themselves both at Home and at School Home Involvement.

Parents were first asked: What are some home activities you engage in toward your child's education? Analysis of the distribution of responses provided by parents on which home involvement activities they engage to assist their child education reveal that more parents did involve themselves in Monitoring the study time (22%) and assisting child with homework (22%). Parent also involved themselves in selecting television programmes for the child (14.6%), inspecting homework (9.8%), buying books for child (7.3%), monitoring child's playing (7.3%), Discussions (7.3%),

Some responses provided by parents are as follows:

"To help him do his homework if I have the idea" [Parent 1, deprived]

"Sometimes I help her with what she does not understand and also make sure they study after school and monitor their playing times. I also give them whatever is requested for like books, pens, etc." [Parent 33, deprived]

"...to help him do his homework, I do advise him and also tell him educative stories" [Parent 3, deprived]

"doing homework, downloading learning materials online and monitoring the internet usage" [Parent 7, deprived]

"I select TV programs for my child, we discuss plans toward child education" [Parent 8, deprived]

"I ensure he come home early so he can do his house chores in time, and then can learn." [Parent 15, deprived]

"Prescribing the kind of TV programs and managing her playing time" [Parent 17, deprived]

Least among home activities which parent involve themselves in were the buying learning materials (2.4%), taking children to library (2.4%), and reading educative stories (2.4%).

It is worth noting that the proportion of parents who involved themselves in all the outline home activities were very low. A result which suggest low involvement of parents in a home involvement activities. The finding are consistent with Gyamfi and Pobbi (2016) who posit that that Ghanaian parents seem to pay more attention to selecting television programme for child, setting time for children to return from school, and ensuring child homework is done but give less attention to taking children to libraries.

A summary of home involvement activities of parents across type of district is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Multiple Bar Chart of Home Involvement Activities across District type

There were activities outlined by parents in non-deprived districts which were not common with parents in deprived districts these included advise and encouragement to child (7.7%), monitoring of internet usage (3.8%), taking child to library (3.8%) and reading of educative stories to child (3.8%).

The School involvement activities which engage in include the analysis of the distribution of responses provided by parents on which school involvement activities they engage to assist their child education reveal that most parents did attend Parent and Teacher Association meetings (PTA). This was evident in an estimated percentage of 50% of all responses provided. The next activity parent did involve in was communications with teachers and school. This accounted for 38.2% of all responses. Some parents also noted that they attended other school programs (5.9% of all responses) like cultural festivals and speech and prize giving days, and other noted that they send child to school (5.9%).

Some of the responses provided by parents are outlined as follows:

“By taking him to school and bringing him home.” [Parent 1, non-deprived]

“Attending PTA and paying fees.” [Parent 2, non-deprived]

“I regularly communicate with the child teacher..., I also attend PTA meetings to make relevant inputs.” [Parent 6, non-deprived]

“I attend PTA meetings and school cultural festivals.” [Parent 7, non-deprived]

"I participate in programmes organised by my child school." [Parent deprived]

"I make voluntary visit to her school ascertain her performance and behaviour in School."
[Parent 23, deprived]

A summary of school involvement activities of parents across type of district is presented in Figure 4:

Figure 4: Multiple Bar Chart of School Involvement Activities across District type

The graph reveals that parental school involvement activities for parents across district type seem to be very similar. Only marginal differences were observed for the activities attending PTA and communicating with teachers. The results suggest that parents across district type mostly attend PTA meeting and communicate with child's teachers and is supported by Chowa, Anson, and Osei-Akoto (2012).

OB3: To identify barriers that affect parental involvement among deprived and non-deprived districts Barriers to Parental Involvement

In response to the barriers which hindered parents' involvement in schools. Four key issues were mentioned. These were the lack of time due to work schedules, the lack of ability to assist child, the financial constraint, and lack of time due to social functions. Analysis of responses result reveal that lack of time due to work schedules (41.2% of all responses) was the leading barrier of parental involvement in child education. This was followed by financial constrains which accounted for (29.4% of all responses). This was followed closely by the lack of ability on the path of parents to sometimes assist the child at home (23.5% of all responses). The last factor was the lack of time due to social functions (5.9% of all responses)

Some responses from some participants were as follows:

“As a single mother I sometimes get tired after work and there are other home activities which also stress me up when I get home. As a result, I am not able to involve myself so much in the studies of my child.” [Parent 4, Non-deprived]

“When I don’t have idea about her homework, he brings home” [Parent 26, non-deprived]

“Sometimes I am busy at work and get home a bit late due to traffic” [Parent 10, non-deprived]

“Sometimes we are not able to help much with the homework since I did not have much formal education” [Parent 23, deprived]

Some parents also complained of financial hardships, and lack of time due to social functions. For example, a parent commented:

“Things are a bit hard financially so when fees are increased, I am not able to pay. This sometimes discourages me from attending school meetings” [Parent 31, deprived]

A summary of barriers to parents’ involvement across type of district is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Multiple Bar Chart of Barriers of Parental Involvement across District type

The graph depicts that whereas work schedule was the most dominant barrier to involvement for parents from non-deprived districts as there were mostly the leading barriers to involvement for parents from deprived districts were the lack of knowledge on homework, and financial constraints. Aside the lack of time due to work schedule some parents from deprived districts also noted that did not get time as a result of social functions.

For example, a parent commented:

"...lack of funds, time constrains due to social activities [Parent 32, deprived]

With regard to the financial of parent in rural communities Donkor et al. (2013) mention that some of these parents who claim they are not able to afford school fees, lunch fees and learning materials for children spend much money to look good on special occasions, such as funerals.

5. Recommendations

With regards to the practical implications of findings, Schools and teachers should also create conducive environment which will foster questions, comments and controlled visitation from parents.

As work-related issues consistently remain a major barrier in many studies there should be a means to bridge the gap by introducing technologies which can allow parents to assist their children at home from work.

Although the study examined motivations and involvement behaviours of parents in disadvantaged/deprived districts it does not do so for parents of disabled children. Hence further research can be conducted to instigate the motivation of parents for disabled.

6. Conclusion

Parental involvement as a behaviour can be predicted by the attitudes of parents, their Social norm and perceived behavioural control, with attitude of parents having the most pronounce influence. These three factors can be improved by improved through sensitisation of parents on the importance of their involvement, how to involve themselves at home and school, and by creating school environments which are welcoming enough for parents so they can communicate freely with teaching on the progress of their children. Schools and teachers' positive comments on parent's participation, and feedback of child performances to parents are relevant toward influencing some parents and need not be underestimated.

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